

Clinical, Hematological, and Biochemical Profile of Anemia in the Pediatric Age Group

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia is a prevalent condition in pediatric populations, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where it significantly impacts growth, cognitive development, and overall health. Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is the most common form, often associated with nutritional deficiencies. Despite available interventions, anemia remains a major public health challenge, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of its clinical, hematological, and biochemical profiles.

Aim: To evaluate the clinical, hematological, and biochemical profiles of anemia in pediatric patients to better understand the underlying causes and inform targeted interventions.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted on 80 pediatric patients aged 6 months to 15 years, diagnosed with anemia. Data collection included clinical assessments, hematological parameters (hemoglobin, hematocrit, RBC indices), and biochemical markers (serum iron, ferritin, TIBC). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The study found that 60% of patients had moderate anemia, with a mean hemoglobin level of 8.1 ± 1.6 g/dL. Microcytic hypochromic anemia was the most prevalent type, observed in 60% of patients, indicating a high prevalence of iron deficiency. Biochemical analysis revealed that 65% of patients had low serum iron levels, 70% had low ferritin levels, and 60% had elevated TIBC. A significant correlation was found between hemoglobin and serum ferritin levels ($r=0.65$, $p < 0.001$), emphasizing the role of iron deficiency in pediatric anemia.

Conclusion: Iron deficiency anaemia is common in children, especially younger ones, according to the study. Anaemia management requires comprehensive diagnostic evaluations due to the high link between haematological and biochemical markers. Preventing long-term problems requires early recognition and management.

Recommendations: The findings underscore the importance of public health strategies focused on nutritional supplementation and education to reduce the burden of anemia. Regular screening and timely interventions should be implemented, particularly in high-risk populations.

Keywords: Anemia, Pediatric, Iron Deficiency, Hematological Profile, Biochemical Markers.

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Introduction

Anemia is a significant public health concern, particularly in pediatric populations, where it can have profound impacts on growth, development, and overall health. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that anemia affects nearly 42% of children under five years of age globally, with the highest burden in low- and middle-income countries [1]. Anemia in children is primarily caused by nutritional deficiencies, especially iron deficiency, which accounts for approximately 50% of all cases [2]. Other contributing factors include infectious diseases, chronic inflammation, and genetic disorders, all of which can exacerbate the condition's severity and complexity.

Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is the most prevalent type of anemia in children and is associated with adverse developmental outcomes, including impaired cognitive and motor development, reduced academic performance, and weakened immune function. The early years of life are particularly critical, as rapid growth during infancy and early childhood increases the demand for iron and other micronutrients. If left untreated, anemia can lead to long-term health consequences, including stunted growth and increased susceptibility to infections [3].

Recent studies have highlighted the alarming prevalence of anemia among pediatric populations, particularly in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa.

For instance, a study conducted in India reported that 58.6% of children under five were anemic, with 27.7% having moderate to severe anemia [4]. Similarly, in Sub-Saharan Africa, nearly 60% of children under five are estimated to be anemic, with iron deficiency being the leading cause [5]. These statistics underscore the urgent need for effective public health interventions to combat anemia in these regions.

In clinical settings, anemia in children is typically diagnosed through hematological parameters such as hemoglobin concentration, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), and red blood cell (RBC) indices. However, biochemical markers like serum ferritin, serum iron, and total iron-binding capacity (TIBC) are essential for identifying the underlying cause, particularly in distinguishing IDA from other forms of anemia [6]. The integration of these diagnostic tools allows for a more comprehensive assessment, enabling tailored treatment strategies that address the specific needs of each patient.

Despite the availability of diagnostic and therapeutic interventions, anemia remains a persistent challenge in pediatric healthcare. Factors such as socioeconomic status, dietary habits, and access to healthcare services significantly influence the prevalence and severity of anemia. Therefore, understanding the clinical, hematological, and biochemical profiles of anemia in children is crucial for developing targeted interventions aimed at reducing the burden of this condition.

This study aims to evaluate the clinical, hematological, and biochemical profile of anemia in the pediatric age group.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Pediatrics, ESI-PGIMS, Basaidarapur, New Delhi, India.

Participants: The study included 80 pediatric patients aged between 6 months and 15 years, who were diagnosed with anemia based on clinical evaluation and laboratory findings.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pediatric patients aged 6 months to 15 years.
- Patients diagnosed with anemia (hemoglobin levels below age-specific thresholds).
- Patients whose guardians provided informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with congenital hematological disorders such as thalassemia or sickle cell disease.

- Patients with chronic illnesses such as renal or hepatic disorders.
- Patients who had received a blood transfusion within the last three months.
- Patients whose guardians did not provide informed consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was employed, and all eligible patients during the study period were included. Information bias was minimized by using standardized and validated methods for data collection. Observer bias was minimized by having the same investigator perform all the clinical evaluations and laboratory analyses.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of medical record review, clinical examination, and laboratory investigations. A structured data collection form was used to record patient demographics, clinical history, physical examination findings, hematological parameters (hemoglobin, hematocrit, RBC indices, etc.), and biochemical parameters (serum iron, ferritin, total iron-binding capacity, etc.).

Procedure: Eligible patients were identified based on the inclusion criteria, and informed consent was obtained from their guardians. A thorough clinical examination was conducted, including the assessment of growth parameters, signs of pallor, and other physical findings related to anemia.

Blood samples were collected from each patient for complete blood count (CBC), peripheral smear examination, and relevant biochemical tests, including serum iron studies. All clinical and laboratory data were recorded on the standardized data collection form.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic, clinical, and laboratory data. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD) or median with interquartile range (IQR) depending on the distribution. Comparative analyses were performed using the Chi-square test for categorical variables and the t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables, as appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

The study included 80 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia, with an age range of 6 months to 15 years. The mean age of the participants was 7.8 ± 4.2 years. Of the total participants, 45 (56.3%) were male, and 35 (43.7%) were female, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.29:1. The majority of the patients (40%) were between 6 months and 5 years of age,

followed by 30% in the 6-10 years age group, and 30% in the 11-15 years age group.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Frequency (n=80)	Percentage (%)
Age Group		
6 months – 5 years	32	40.0
6 – 10 years	24	30.0
11 – 15 years	24	30.0
Gender		
Male	45	56.3
Female	35	43.7
Nutritional Status		
Underweight (BMI < 18.5)	48	60.0
Normal weight (BMI 18.5-24.9)	32	40.0
Overweight (BMI ≥ 25)	0	0.0

The most common clinical presentation observed was pallor, present in 68 (85%) of the patients. Other symptoms included fatigue (70%), weakness (65%), and shortness of breath (45%). Additionally, 20% of the children had a history of pica.

Table 2: Clinical Symptoms and Signs in Pediatric Patients with Anemia

Clinical Feature	Frequency (n=80)	Percentage (%)
Pallor	68	85.0
Fatigue	56	70.0
Weakness	52	65.0
Shortness of Breath	36	45.0
Pica	16	20.0

The mean hemoglobin (Hb) level among the patients was 8.1 ± 1.6 g/dL. Hemoglobin levels were categorized as mild (10-11.9 g/dL), moderate (7-9.9 g/dL), and severe anemia (<7 g/dL). The majority of patients (47.5%) had moderate anemia, followed by 30% with mild anemia, and 22.5% with severe anemia.

Mean corpuscular volume (MCV) ranged from 60 to 88 fL with a mean of 72.5 ± 7.3 fL, indicating a

prevalence of microcytic anemia in the cohort. Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) had a mean value of 30.5 ± 2.2 g/dL. Peripheral smear analysis revealed that 60% of patients had microcytic hypochromic anemia, 25% had normocytic normochromic anemia, and 15% had macrocytic anemia.

Table 3: Hematological Parameters of Study Participants

Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	8.1 ± 1.6	4.5 – 11.5
Hematocrit (%)	26.2 ± 4.5	15.3 – 35.1
MCV (fL)	72.5 ± 7.3	60 – 88
MCHC (g/dL)	30.5 ± 2.2	24.7 – 35.2
Anemia Severity		
Mild (10-11.9 g/dL)	24	30.0
Moderate (7-9.9 g/dL)	38	47.5
Severe (<7 g/dL)	18	22.5
Peripheral Smear Findings		
Microcytic hypochromic	48	60.0
Normocytic normochromic	20	25.0
Macrocytic	12	15.0

Serum iron levels had a mean value of 32.5 ± 10.2 μ g/dL, with 65% of patients having iron deficiency (serum iron < 30 μ g/dL). Serum ferritin levels were found to be low in 70% of patients, with a mean ferritin level of 18.4 ± 6.3 ng/mL. Total iron-binding capacity (TIBC) was elevated in 60% of patients, with a mean TIBC of 420 ± 80 μ g/dL.

Table 4: Biochemical Parameters of Study Participants

Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD	Frequency (%)
Serum Iron ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	32.5 $\pm$ 10.2	
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	18.4 $\pm$ 6.3	
TIBC ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	420 $\pm$ 80	
Iron Deficiency		52 (65.0)
Low Ferritin		56 (70.0)
Elevated TIBC		48 (60.0)

A significant correlation was found between hemoglobin levels and serum ferritin levels (Pearson's correlation coefficient, $r = 0.65$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that lower hemoglobin levels were associated with lower serum ferritin levels. Additionally, the severity of anemia was significantly associated with serum iron levels ($p = 0.002$) and TIBC ($p = 0.015$).

Table 5: Correlation Between Hemoglobin Levels and Biochemical Parameters

Parameter	Pearson's r	p-value
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	0.65	<0.001
Serum Iron ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	0.42	0.002
TIBC ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	-0.30	0.015

Discussion

The study involved 80 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia, with a mean age of 7.8 years. The demographic analysis revealed a slightly higher prevalence of anemia in males (56.3%) compared to females (43.7%). The majority of the patients were under five years of age, highlighting that younger children are particularly vulnerable to anemia.

Clinically, pallor was the most common symptom, observed in 85% of the patients, followed by fatigue, weakness, and shortness of breath. The frequent occurrence of these symptoms underscores the significant impact of anemia on the daily functioning and well-being of children. Additionally, a notable percentage of children (20%) exhibited pica, a behavior often associated with iron deficiency.

Hematological analysis showed that the average hemoglobin level among the patients was 8.1 g/dL, with nearly half of the cohort suffering from moderate anemia. Microcytic hypochromic anemia was the predominant type, found in 60% of the patients, indicating a strong association with iron deficiency. The presence of severe anemia in 22.5% of the patients is concerning and suggests a need for urgent medical intervention in these cases.

Biochemically, the study confirmed that a significant proportion of the patients had iron deficiency, with 65% showing low serum iron levels and 70% exhibiting low serum ferritin levels. Elevated TIBC, found in 60% of the patients, further supports the diagnosis of iron deficiency anemia. The strong positive correlation between hemoglobin and serum ferritin levels ($r = 0.65$) indicates that lower hemoglobin levels are closely associated with depleted iron stores.

Overall, the results highlight the high prevalence of iron deficiency anemia among the pediatric

population studied. The correlation between hematological and biochemical parameters emphasizes the importance of comprehensive diagnostic evaluations in managing anemia. These findings suggest that early detection and intervention are crucial, particularly in younger children, to prevent the long-term consequences of untreated anemia. The study calls for targeted nutritional and healthcare strategies to address the underlying causes of anemia and improve the health outcomes for affected children.

A study explored the clinicohematological profile of anemia in pediatric patients ranging from newborns to 18 years of age. The study identified that microcytic hypochromic anemia was the most prevalent morphological type, with iron deficiency being the leading cause. The study also highlighted that hematological and biochemical investigations are crucial for early diagnosis and prevention of anemia-related complications [7].

A research focused on the biochemical and hematological profiles of anemia in pediatric patients in India. It revealed that iron deficiency anemia was the most common, particularly in children aged 1-6 years. The study underscored the importance of early detection using hematological and biochemical tests to guide treatment strategies [8].

A study provided insights into the hematological profile of severe anemia in children aged below 5 years. It found that microcytic hypochromic anemia was predominant, emphasizing the need for timely intervention to address nutritional deficiencies [9].

A study aimed to evaluate the clinical features and basic hematological parameters of anemia in children aged 6 months to 14 years. It concluded that iron deficiency anemia was the most common type, often associated with acute gastroenteritis and respiratory symptoms [10].

A retrospective study analyzing the hematological profile of anemia in children aged 1 month to 14 years. The study found that nutritional anemia was the most common cause, highlighting the need for preventive measures and nutritional support [11].

Conclusion

The study highlighted the high prevalence of iron deficiency anemia among pediatric patients. The strong correlation between hematological parameters and biochemical markers underscored the importance of comprehensive evaluations in diagnosing and managing anemia in this population. The findings suggest a need for targeted interventions to address nutritional deficiencies and improve the overall health status of children affected by anemia.

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